

Suchresultate zur Studie Digital mobility outcomes – grey literature

ACM Digital Library	123
ProQuest Dissertations	887
OpenGrey	62
National Information Center	132
clinicaltrials.gov	2353

Reference files:

acm.enlx
proquest.enlx
open grey.enlx
hsr_project_search_result.xlsx
clinicaltrials.enlx

Search string as for IEEE Xplore

("chronic obstructive lung" OR "chronic obstructive pulmonary" OR copd OR "chronic airway obstruction" OR "chronic airflow obstruction" OR parkinson OR "multiple sclerosis" OR demyelinated OR demyelination OR "hip fracture" OR "femoral fracture" OR "femur fracture") AND (walk OR walking OR step OR speed OR gait OR spatiotemporal OR stride OR swing OR stance OR "single support" OR "double support" OR ambulation OR ambulatory)

(for clinicaltrials.gov without "chronic airflow obstruction")

02.12.2019